

Current and future trends in lithium-ion battery electrode production machinery: A comprehensive review

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Abstract

In response to the rising energy demand due to global population growth, the consumption of non-renewable energy sources has also increased, bringing with it various environmental issues. To overcome these environmental challenges, the net-zero emissions by 2050 policy has been adopted and the focus shifted toward alternative and sustainable energy sources. Among the alternative energy sources, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) dominate the energy storage market and countries have made serious efforts to develop their LIB value chain. LIB machinery is one of the most important building blocks of the LIB value chain since it has a significant impact on product quality, energy consumption, cost-effectiveness, and factory efficiency. Especially, electrode fabrication equipment and methods directly affect the quality of the electrode from electrochemical, microstructural, and mechanical aspects, and thus the performance, reliability, and service life of the produced battery. Based on these considerations, this paper presents a comprehensive review of the machines used in the electrode production steps of LIBs. In this regard, the present review consists of two major sections. In the first section, electrode manufacturing processes, encompassing mixing, coating, drying, and calendaring as well as their working principles, operating parameters, applications, and effects in the relevant production processes were elaborated. In addition, detailed equipment comparisons were conducted for each electrode fabrication step, including their advantages, disadvantages, maturity levels, and the production scales at which each machine is typically used. In the second main section, a future outlook on electrode production was provided, discussing the integration of digitalization, flexible manufacturing, academia-industry collaboration, and the adoption of sustainable and next-generation technologies such as dry manufacturing, highlighting potential directions for machinery development and the evolving needs of the LIB industry. This review aims to provide a valuable guide for researchers and industry professionals, covering both the evaluation of electrode manufacturing processes and equipment, and the future directions of battery production.

Keywords: Lithium-ion batteries, battery production machinery, electrode manufacturing, electrode quality, battery value chain

1. Introduction

Global population growth and accelerated industrialization cause a significant increase in energy demand [1,2]. In order to avoid or minimize threats such as climate change and global warming, which result from the use of fossil fuels as the dominant source (~80% of the total energy supply in 2021), to take precautions for decreasing natural energy resources, and to meet the rising energy need, the transition to renewable and sustainable energy sources has become vital [3–5]. Researchers and policymakers focus on the wider use of more sustainable and low-carbon energy sources such as energy storage, solar, and wind [6,7]. Among the energy storage systems, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) dominate the market thanks to their large range of application areas including electric vehicles, portable electronic devices, and smart power grids with their advantages such as high energy density, long cycle life, high reliability, and stable charging-discharging conditions [8,9]. However, large-scale deployment of LIBs still requires greater attention to the sustainability of raw materials, durability, active material supply risk, safety standards, component recyclability, and cost efficiency [10–12]. Considering these requirements, many organizations and financing programs have been established around the world, such as the European Battery Alliance (EBA) in the European Union (EU) [13], the United States Advanced Battery Consortium (USABC) in the United States (U.S.) [14], and the China Electric Vehicle Association (CEVA) in China [15] to improve the LIB value chain and ecosystem.

A conventional LIB electrochemical cell consists of two electrodes, namely the cathode and the anode, an electrolyte, and an electrolyte-permeable separator [16,17]. The electrodes act as hosts for lithium ions (Li-ions) and store chemical energy to be converted into electrical energy via reversible electrochemical reactions [18]. The electrolyte transports Li-ions between the electrodes and forces the electrons outside the cell during charging and discharging [17,19]. In addition, the separator keeps the electrodes physically isolated from each other to prevent electrical short circuits, while allowing the Li-ions flow [20]. Research on enhancing cell chemistry materials is crucial to achieving better performance, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable batteries [21]. There are many studies in the literature on improving cell components [8,22–27]. On the other hand, the cell production process is another essential factor that determines important features such as battery quality, safety, and service life [28]. Electrode manufacturing, cell assembly, and cell finishing stages are the main phases of the LIB production procedure. Moreover, LIB fabrication is an intricate process due to the fact that individual steps are heavily interlinked and affect each other [29]. For example, during slurry mixing, the viscosity of the mixture must be optimized to obtain a processable slurry for the coating step. Too high viscosity makes it difficult to achieve uniformly coated electrodes and too low viscosity causes spread and precipitation after coating [30,31]. Thereby, a slurry with non-optimized viscosity causes an inappropriate electrode coating process, which leads to the production of a low-performance battery or generate scrap [32]. Moreover, the equipment used in production are crucial for aspects such as scalability, energy cost, precision, and ease of use. For instance, in the coating step, the doctor blade setup is mostly used for laboratory-scale production due to its simple use and cost-effectiveness, while the slot die coater, which has high precision and is suitable for continuous production, is generally used in pilot-scale and industrial-scale manufacturing [33]. Furthermore, battery cell production machinery plays an important role in the LIB value chain as it influences

every aspect such as production and energy efficiency, cell quality, ecologic production and sustainability, and cost-effectiveness. Accordingly, leading manufacturers such as CATL, BYD, LG Energy Solution, and SK on closely monitor and invest in advancements in battery production machinery and technologies, which constitutes a key factor in maintaining their leadership position in the industry [34–37]. Optimization of machinery and process variables contributes to increasing material efficiency and minimizing production-related expenses such as energy and scrap costs [38]. Therefore, to improve cell production, in addition to material design, the relationship between the applied production method, process parameters, and proper machine selection for each manufacturing step must be well understood. Nevertheless, little attention has been paid to investigate the machines used for cell production in the literature and there are limited studies related to battery cell manufacturing machinery [21,32,39].

The development, manufacturing, and implementation of batteries are key to the ambition for transition to a climate-neutral economy, considering their critical role in the deployment of zero-emission vehicles and the storage of intermittent renewable energy sources [40]. In 2022, Europe contributed approximately 8.5% to global LIB manufacturing capacity, while China and the U.S. accounted for about 76% and 7%, respectively [41]. The EU Commission encourages the boosting of the LIB value chain to gain competitive power and respond to increasing energy demand by having a larger share of the battery market [42]. EBA is one of the most important moves made by the EU commission in this regard and is making rapid progress towards creating an integrated and competitive battery value chain in Europe, from battery cell production to key areas such as production machinery, raw materials, and battery management systems [42]. In addition, the European Green Deal Industrial Plan aims to increase Europe's industrial capacity and develop green technologies and products [43]. In line with the European Green Deal, the LIB market also has an important responsibility as it is a growing and developing field. From the scope of the LIB industry, LIB production machinery is vital in achieving the goals of lower greenhouse gas emissions, less energy consumption for production, reduced scrap generation, and increased plant efficiency.

In this paper, we review various machines used in LIB electrode manufacturing and discuss the associated future trends and challenges. In the first main section, the equipment were classified based on their application steps, including mixing, coating, drying and calendering. Then, their working principles, important operating parameters and applications in the electrode production were investigated. Investigated mixing equipment includes hydrodynamic shear mixer and ball mill mixer as established methods, while ultrasonic mixer and extruder represent novel approaches. In addition, coating techniques comprise slot die coater, doctor blade, and comma bar coater as conventional methods, along with innovative strategies such as dry calendering via roll press and electrostatic spray deposition. Moreover, drying processes feature hot air convective dryer as traditional method, whereas infrared radiation dryer and microwave dryer are considered emerging alternatives. Lastly, the calendering step focuses on roll press equipment. Furthermore, the advantages and disadvantages, maturity levels, scalabilities from laboratory to mass production, and impacts on the final performance of each machine were analyzed and comprehensive comparisons were conducted for each electrode production step. Additionally, the second main section addresses integration of different digitalization approaches into electrode

production to reduce scrap generation, implementing flexible production lines for diverse battery designs and chemistries, importance of fostering academia-industry collaboration in battery value chain development, and the significance of integrating sustainable and next generation alternatives including dry coating equipment into industrial production.

2. Lithium-Ion Cell Production and Machinery

Although various manufacturers have distinct cell designs—such as prismatic (e.g., ACC, Gotion), cylindrical (e.g., Verkor, Panasonic), and pouch (e.g., Univercell, SK Innovation)—the basic steps used to produce cells are remarkably similar [44]. As mentioned earlier, a typical battery cell is produced through electrode fabrication, cell assembly, and cell finishing stages. Moreover, these main stages include several steps, as illustrated in Figure 1. In sequence, slurry mixing, coating, drying, and calendaring are the key steps of electrode fabrication. In order, slitting of electrodes and separators, stacking/winding, tab welding, packaging, electrolyte filling and cell sealing are the following steps to complete the cell assembly process. In the final stage, cell finishing includes cell formation and aging steps.

In this section, we provide a brief description of the sequential steps involved in the electrode fabrication of battery cells and an extensive review of the various machines used to accomplish these steps.

Figure 1. Schematic of the LIB production stages and corresponding steps. Inspired by Zanotto et al. [45]

2.1. Slurry Mixing

In a traditional LIB production, the electrode slurry consists of active material (AM), conductive additive (CA), binder, and solvent. In the slurry mixture, the AM serves as the lithium reservoir or host and the CA improves the electrical conductivity throughout the coating, while the binder holds the AM and the CA particles together and adheres them to the current collector [46]. The electrode slurry is prepared by mixing all of the constituents together with the solvent to form

a homogenous slurry. The slurry mixing process aims to break up particle agglomerates and produce a homogenous mixture. This means that the viscosity of the obtained slurry must be appropriate relative to van der Waals interactions between particles and the sedimentation rate of the particles in the slurry must be low according to Stokes' law [21]. In LIB manufacturing, achieving optimum slurry properties is crucial as it has a direct impact on the final electrode quality and hence electrochemical performance of the produced battery. In addition, the slurry mixing step represents 7.9% of the total production cost [44]. Therefore, the selection of mixing equipment and application of appropriate mixing method have a direct impact on producing high-performance, high-quality and cost-effective batteries. Hydrodynamic shear mixers, ball mills, ultrasonic mixers and extruders are widely used mixers during LIB production.

2.1.1. Hydrodynamic Shear Mixers

Hydrodynamic shear mixers (HSM) are advanced mixing machines that enable the production of homogeneous mixtures by applying shear forces. In HSMs, the mixing process utilizes shear forces generated by the relative motion between the rotor and stator parts [47]. The functionality of the rotor is to provide the shear forces required for the movement of the liquid and to mix the components by rotating, while the stator is a fixed part with a perforated structure that allows the solid particles and liquid to pass through [48,49]. This structure creates turbulent stresses during the flow of the mixture and created stresses help break up the agglomerates [50], as demonstrated in Figure 2. For the rotor, different kinds of blade shapes, like axial and radial, can be used, while for the stator, different types of holes, such as circles or straight lines, can be applicable [49]. The speed of the rotor usually varies from 10 to 50 m/s and these high speeds enable the mixer to achieve shear rates ranging from 20,000 to 100,000 s^{-1} [51].

HSMs are widely used in many industrial applications requiring high energy density, such as homogenization, dispersion, emulsification, grinding, and dissolving [50]. For example, in slurry preparation processes used in LIB production, HSMs homogenize the mixture through hydrodynamic forces controlled by the flow shear rate, particle cross-sectional area, and dynamic viscosity of the liquid [52]. This mixing process consists of two sub-processes: the breaking up of particle clusters under the influence of shear forces and the reassociation of clusters into the slurry when these forces are reduced [48,53]. On the other hand, hydrodynamic shear-based mixing processes can lead to fragmentation of binder molecules, especially when applied at high-intensity [54,55]. Such fragmentation not only risks binder performance but can also contribute to increased material waste due to batch rejection or reprocessing. Therefore, the structural integrity of the binder should be maintained while adjusting the mixing intensity. In the cathode production of lithium-ion batteries, it is necessary to have an appropriate size distribution of AM and CA particles to obtain an ideal mixture. In particular, the mixing of very fine primary particles (less than 100 nm) often forms larger clusters in the mixtures obtained with HSM [56]. Increasing the mixing intensity in order to reduce these clusters to smaller sizes can damage the binders, which may negatively impact battery performance. For these reasons, attempts to break up these clusters through higher mixing intensity can lead to additional material loss, increasing both waste generation and overall battery costs. Therefore, the use of this technology should be carefully evaluated depending on the particle sizes and binder properties.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of a) HSM, and b) deagglomeration and mixing of deagglomerated particles

Since the HSMs are regarded as a mature technology, they are easy to scale up economically. Numerous common industrial HSMs exist such as planetary mixers, Rushton turbines, and rotary drum mixers. As the energy distribution is concentrated in the mixing head, industrial HSMs use more power than conventional mechanical mixers [57]. According to the review of published patents and offers from LIB machinery suppliers, the majority of industrial and pilot line LIB slurry mixing methods rely on different forms of HSMs, especially planetary mixers to prepare large-volume slurries [32,58–61]. Additionally, a magnetic stirrer is a tool that utilizes the hydrodynamic shear effect and is commonly used in laboratory-scale research. Unlike others in terms of structural and working concepts, a magnetic stirrer usually consists of a rotating magnet driven by an electric motor and a magnetic stir bar that is placed inside a container with the mixture. Due to the magnetic field created by the rotating magnet, the magnetic stir bar follows the rotation of the magnet and therefore creates a movement in the mixture and stirs the slurry with a low hydrodynamic shear rate [62].

Liu et al. proposed a new 3D mixer based on the HSM concept to provide effective mixing in all directions [63]. The designed mixer consists of a rotating cylindrical container to generate mixing in the θ -direction, a traditional Rushton turbine for r-direction mixing, an off-centered helical ribbon impeller to provide mixing in the z-direction, and an additional rectangular plate near the wall of the container to scrape off any stagnant or to push the slowly moving slurry during the mixing process (Figure 3). In the study, to compare the effectiveness of the designed mixer, $\text{LiNi}_{0.4}\text{Mn}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (NMC442) based cathode slurries were prepared by using three different mixer as designed 3D mixer, simple Rushton turbine mixer, and ball mill mixer. According to the obtained results, better particle distribution of AM and CA at the electrodes led to a higher capacity in the battery produced with the designed 3D mixer.

Figure 3. Photographs of the developed 3D mixer, **a)** agitator axle, **b)** tank, **c)** rotational axles, **d)** rotational based, **e)** Rushton turbine, **f)** helical ribbon impeller, **g)** vertical plate. Reprinted with permission from [63]

Hoffmann et al. studied the effects of different planetary mixer (Netzsch, Germany) mixing procedures on the performance of ultra-thick $\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (NMC622) based cathode electrodes [64]. The results show that the low shear mixing method provides higher porosity and lower tortuosity, improving Li-ion diffusion in the produced electrodes. In contrast, the application of the high shear mixing approach generates a denser, less porous electrode structure, which can restrict electrolyte diffusion and reduce rate capability under high current densities. In addition, it was discovered that electrodes produced with a low shear process maintained superior energy density even at high current densities and were found to be more suitable for industrial processing. Furthermore, for a detailed analysis of mixing dynamics in double planetary mixers, readers are referred to Tanguy et al.'s work [65].

In their study, Westphal et al. investigated the effect of high intensive dry mixing using a rotary drum mixer (Dispermat CA60, VMA Getzmann, Germany) on the relative electrode resistivity [66]. Based on the results, increasing mixing intensity results in carbon black (CB) and fine graphite particles accumulating on top of the larger AM graphite particles and this leads to a decrease in resistivity due to the inability to establish a long-range conductive network between particles. Similarly, in the study of Haselrieder et al., the influence of applying high-intensity shear forces are analyzed using horizontal rotary drum mixer (Nobilta™, Hosokawa Alpine AG, Germany) in the scope of the performance and structural characteristics of $\text{Li}(\text{Li}-\text{Mn}-\text{Al})_2\text{O}_4/\text{LiNi}_{0.80}\text{Co}_{0.15}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ (LMS/NCA) electrodes [67]. The findings reveal that applying high-intensity shear forces has negative impacts on the rate-capability of LMS electrodes by causing morphological changes. However, it was found that the influence of the mechanical stress was dramatically lower in LMS/NCA blends, creating a new processing pathway for mechanically sensitive spinel-structured AMs.

The electrochemical performance and stability characteristics of polyphosphazene-based gel polymer electrolytes in combination with Li-metal anodes were researched by Jankowsky et al.

[68]. In their study, LiFePO_4 (LFP) based electrodes were prepared with a high energy stirrer (T 18 ULTRA-TURRAX®, IKA, Germany); however, no evaluation was provided regarding the impacts of the used stirrer.

In their research, Bockholt et al. investigated the effects of four different mixer using —rotary drum mixer, super high shear mixer (Nobilta™, Hosokawa Micron Ltd., Runcorn, UK), intensive mixer (Eirich, Germany), and planetary mixer (Netzsch, Germany)— on CB distribution, pore structure, and binder-CB network formation in $\text{LiNi}_{1/3}\text{Co}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$ (NMC111) electrodes [69]. According to the obtained results, since the rotary drum mixer only provides distributive mixing, it left large CB agglomerates in the bulk without achieving a homogenous distribution. In contrast, the CB agglomerates were strongly broken up by the shear forces applied by the super-high shear mixer, causing larger pore sizes and a reduced specific conductivity. Moreover, intensive mixer and planetary mixer effectively ruptured the CB agglomerates and achieved a finer, more homogeneous distribution and a smaller pore structure, leading to improved bulk electrical conductivity and electrochemical performance.

In the study by Ponrouch and Palacín, the effects of different slurry mixing methods on the microstructure and homogeneity of mesocarbon microbeads (MCMB) graphite and Co_3O_4 composite electrodes were comprehensively examined, and impact on electrochemical performance were evaluated [70]. The initial microstructure of the AM and the spherical morphology of MCMB particles were preserved due to the soft mixing effect of the magnetic stirrer. However, in the electrodes prepared using the magnetic stirrer without the ultrasonication effect, insufficient homogeneity was observed, which resulted in lower capacity rates. Additionally, the use of a magnetic stirrer in combination with ultrasonication (magnetic stirring for 15 h, the vial containing the slurry being placed in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min every 5 h) enhanced the homogeneity of the mixture and improved the electrochemical performance of the resulting electrodes. Overall, this combination provided positive results in terms of both homogeneity and performance.

Dominguez et al. investigated effect of mixing speed on the rheological properties of NMC622-based electrodes through different slurry component combinations by using high shear mixer (Dispermat CV3-PLUS, VMA-Getzmann, Germany) [71]. The authors emphasize that the mixing protocol is a critical parameter for achieving optimal electrode manufacturing. They report that mixing speed significantly affects the viscosity of NMC + CB and NMC + CB + PVDF slurries, whereas its effect on CB + PVDF mixtures is negligible. Furthermore, the NMC + CB network is highly sensitive to shear forces and breaks more easily at higher speeds. Moreover, frequency sweeps revealed elastic behavior at low speeds (2000 rpm), viscous behavior at high speeds (4000 rpm), and a balanced rheological response at the intermediate speed (3000 rpm).

As a result, HSMs are highly effective and advanced technology in producing homogeneous, high-quality mixtures through intense shear forces. These features of HSM technology make them stand out in energy-intensive mixing processes such as homogenization, dispersion and emulsification. With compatible rotor and stator designs, HSMs accommodate various particle sizes and provide a scalable solution suitable for laboratory to industrial production. On the other hand, high shear forces can cause structural damage in binder molecules and hinder the formation

of conductive networks. Therefore, optimization of applied mixing intensity based on binder characteristics and particle size is crucial to maximize the effectiveness of the HSM process and prevent potential material degradation. In contrast, magnetic stirrers—distinct in both structure and working principles compared to other HSMs—offer specific advantages for laboratory applications. In this method, the application of low hydrodynamic shear forces maintains the structural integrity of sensitive materials such as binders and offers a cost-effective, easy-to-use solution. However, magnetic stirrers have challenges in high energy and homogeneity required application because they may struggle to break down the dense agglomerates effectively due to the low hydrodynamic shear forces. Consequently, magnetic stirrers are ideal for low-intensity mixing processes in laboratory research.

2.1.2. Ball Mill Mixers

Ball mill mixers (BMMs) are highly efficient machines used for simultaneously grinding and mixing materials to achieve the desired size of particles and uniform mixtures. The ball milling method can be implemented using various types of containers (or bottles, jars) and balls. For instance, the containers can be of different sizes and made of ceramic, metal, or polymer materials, while the grinding balls can be made of steel or ceramic (WC, Si₃N₄, ZrO₂, etc.) [72]. This variety is important depending on the process to be applied and the characteristics of the materials to be milled and mixed. Ball milling is based on the principle of simultaneously grinding and mixing particles by the rotational movement of grinding balls located in a container [72]. In the process, the components are exposed to shear and impact forces induced by the balls, enhancing the kinetic energy of the grinding media and thereby the efficiency of the process [73].

The final material characteristics are influenced by several factors during the ball milling process, examples of which include the type of machine, dimensions of the container, the composition of the grinding ball, and the ball-to-powder ratio (BPR) [74]. The speed, duration, atmosphere (inert or reactive gas), medium (dry or wet) and temperature of the milling process, as well as the contaminants that may be mixed into the powders as a result of the use of organic lubricants, directly affect the properties such as particle size distribution of the material, degree of irregularity or amorphization and final stoichiometry [75]. Furthermore, comprehensive control and monitoring of all these parameters determine the quality of the produced material.

BMMs can be classified into high-energy and low-energy categories in terms of their effectiveness in grinding processes. High-energy ball mills can reduce particles to microscopic sizes by performing grinding operations at high speeds. In this category, attritor ball mill is a machine that grinds and blends ingredients by using beads activated by an agitator to create friction and impact forces [76]. The powder to be milled is placed in a tank and the grinding process is carried out with grinding balls set in motion by a vertical shaft with horizontal arms rotating at a speed of 60 to 350 rpm [77]. Attritor ball mills can be used from laboratory-scale to industrial-scale productions. Another example of high-energy milling is a shaker mill (or vibratory mill) that shakes the container along a complex path combining front and back swings with short-term lateral movements, achieving a motion resembling an infinity sign to effectively grind and mix constituents through impact, shear, and friction forces. Generally, shaker mills operate with a vibration frequency of 20–25 Hz and an acceleration 3–10 times that of gravity [78]. Shaker mills

are more suitable for laboratory applications due to their low container volume (10-20 g) [77]. Among the high-energy milling equipment, planetary ball mills consist of 2 or 4 pots, into which powders to be processed are placed with grinding balls. These containers are fixed on a disk that rotates around its central axis and at the same time each container also rotates around its own axis. The high rotational speeds of the disk, as well as the pots, generate substantial impact and frictional forces that cause the milling balls to collide with the powder particles inside, thereby crushing, grinding, and mixing the ingredients effectively [79]. Planetary ball mills have been widely used for laboratory-scale studies because of their high versatility, allowing several containers to be used at the same time and offering easy handling. Besides, there are also industrial versions that can process up to 3–5 tons per hour [49]. In a tumbler ball mill, a low-energy ball mill, useful kinetic energy is transferred to the materials. This energy transfer occurs through shear and abrasion forces resulting from collisions between the balls and the powder, the pressure loading of the powders compressed between the grinding media or the liner, and impacts caused by the falling grinding media. These low-energy mills produce homogeneous and uniform powders, require a longer time to complete the grinding and mixing process, but are less costly and easier to maintain than high-energy consuming systems [76]. Figure 4 demonstrates the schematic illustration of different types of BMMs.

Figure 4. Schematic illustrations of **a)** planetary BMM, **b)** attritor BMM, **c)** shaker BMM, **d)** tumbler BMM. Adapted with permission from Fernandez-Diaz et al. [49]

BMMs can be utilized in both dry and wet methods. In the dry method, the agglomeration and adhesion of particles are prevented, while in the wet milling method, particles are kept from sticking to the container wall and heat distribution is improved via liquid phase [49]. Dry milling offers the advantages of less processing time and lower operational cost, as well as producing fewer by-products, and is ideal for moisture-sensitive materials. Wet milling, on the other hand, provides better control over particle size and distribution and is therefore highly important in critical applications such as the manufacturing of advanced chemicals and composite materials [80]. Due to the use of toxic solvents in the wet milling method, the dry mixing method is both more ecological and more cost-effective [81,82]. In terms of LIB production, dry mixing is a

remarkable method to eliminate the toxic N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) solvent used in the slurry mixing stage [83].

Within the scope of LIB production, using BMMs plays a crucial role in adjusting material properties. This technique provides mixing, but it also allows the mechanochemical transformation of electrode materials by enabling particle interactions, surface, and volume modifications [84]. For example, it can lead to major changes in the size and structure of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and such modifications can even take place in long-term and low-energy milling processes [85]. However, the effectiveness of BMMs can be hindered by the contamination of ingredients due to wear and prolonged mixing times. Although ball milling provides AM/CA modifications that can improve electrode performance, it also carries the risk of degrading the properties of the starting materials and thus affecting the electrochemical properties of electrodes [86,87]. For this reason, the intensive mechanical forces and prolonged milling times in BMMs can produce partially degraded or unevenly processed material, which directly increases waste generation. Consequently, portions of these altered materials may not meet the quality requirements for electrode fabrication, leading to higher production costs and reduced overall process efficiency. On the other hand, while BMMs provide a finer mixed slurry with smaller AM and CA clusters, especially when compared to HSMs, they can also compromise the morphological characteristics of AM and CA particles [48]. Therefore, this mixing technique may not be recommended in cases where a specific particle morphology is required.

Driscoll et al. studied the basic structural changes of LIB materials induced by ball milling, focusing on pressure-induced phase changes and their influence on electrochemical properties [88]. In the study, Li_2MoO_4 , Li_2MnO_3 , Li_2SnO_3 and Nb_2O_5 materials were milled at different parameters using planetary ball mill (Premium line 7, Fritsch, Germany) and vibratory ball mill (Pulverisette P23, Fritsch, Germany). The obtained results confirmed that ball milling can induce phase transformation due to local pressure and heat effects on Li_2MoO_4 . Furthermore, the layered structures of Li_2MnO_3 and Li_2SnO_3 transformed into disordered rock salt (DRS) phase by the ball milling process; similarly, monoclinic Nb_2O_5 also showed 14% volume decrease by transforming from high-temperature polymorph to low-temperature polymorph orthorhombic Nb_2O_5 phase.

Liu et al. investigated the improvement of the electrochemical behavior of spinel LiMn_2O_4 (LMO) and quaternary spinel $\text{LiCo}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_4$ (LCMO) cathodes [89]. In the study, the LCMO electrode was prepared by prolonged ball milling with 10% CB. Based on the results, ball milled Li/LCMO cell demonstrated the best cyclability, with the capacity reducing from an initial value of 118 to 108 mAh/g after 50 cycles. Two reasons explained by authors are: (i) the utilization of small particles with high surface area is better, (ii) the contact resistance between oxide and carbon particles is reduced after prolonged ball milling.

The research conducted by Nguyen et al. focused on the development of production methods for $\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ (LNMO) composite electrodes [90]. The ingredients were mixed in two different ways, namely ball milling and magnetic stirring. According to the results, ball milling improved electrode performance by ensuring a more uniform distribution; however, the increased surface area raised electrode–electrolyte contact, triggering parasitic reactions and lowering Coulombic efficiency (CE) in the initial cycles. In contrast, since the specific surface areas of the

electrodes prepared by the magnetic stirring method were lower, fewer parasitic reactions occurred in the initial cycles. On the other hand, since the magnetic stirring method is less effective in providing homogeneous distribution of additives, the electrode performance remained lower than the ball milling method in the long term.

Kim et al. studied the enhancement of performance in solid-state LIBs through modifications in the mixing technique used for LiCoO_2 (LCO)-based composite cathode preparation [91]. Three different mixing methods were applied to prepare the electrodes, including manual dry mixing using an agate mortar and pestle, wet mixing in the mortar, and wet mixing with a high-speed ball mixer (Pulverisette 7, Fritsch, Germany). It was found that the cathode prepared by manually dry mixing showed the lowest charge/discharge capacity and the lowest CE in the first cycles. The electrodes prepared by wet mixing in the mortar initially increased capacity and CE by reducing CB deposits; however, after the 30th cycle, there was a significant decrease in capacity and CE. In contrast, the electrode prepared by the wet ball milling maintained higher capacity and nearly 100% CE throughout all cycles.

Cho et al. demonstrated the reduction of silicon oxide through a magnesio-milling process using both a laboratory-scale planetary ball mill and a 5-liter industrial-scale attrition mill to produce high-capacity silicon anodes for LIBs [92]. According to the obtained results, silicon anodes produced with 5L capacity attrition mill preserved 82.8% of the initial capacity after 200 cycles. The attrition milling method provides higher efficiency and homogeneous nanostructure and is superior in terms of cycle stability. Although the planetary ball mill is used in laboratory-scale production, it does not provide as efficient results as the attrition mill on industrial-scale, offering lower capacity and cycle stability.

Wachtler et al. studied the electrochemical performances of four different alloys prepared by mechanical alloying approach using a shaker mill (8000M Mixer-Mill, SPEX, USA) [93]. Among these alloys, the $\text{Sn}_{0.66}\text{Sb}_{0.34}$ alloy exhibited a high cycle life after ball milling, while the Mg_2Si alloy experienced rapid capacity loss despite its high initial capacity. Whereas previously lithiated alloys such as $\text{Li}_4\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}$ and $\text{Li}_4\text{Sn}_{0.72}\text{Sb}_{0.28}$ exhibited a more stable structure with lower capacity. From these findings, it is concluded that ball milling may cause different effects and results according to the material structure.

In brief, BMMs are efficient and advanced equipment for producing homogeneous and high-quality slurry mixtures. These machines are ideal for particularly demanding grinding processes due to their ability to simultaneously mill and blend ingredients with the movement of rotating grinding balls. The flexibility to use a variety of container and ball materials makes BMMs superior in adapting to different material properties and desired particle sizes. In addition, the ability to operate with dry and wet methods offers unique advantages of each method. Dry milling can be faster and more cost-effective; however, wet milling is more controllable in particle size distribution and provides better thermal management during mixing. The usage of BMMs in LIB manufacturing contributes to the mechanochemical transformation of electrode materials, promotes the interaction between particles, changes on the surface and in volume. Such transformations may enhance electrode performance, while long milling processes can contaminate the material and adversely affect electrochemical properties. As a result, BMMs may

not be recommended when specific particle morphology is required, while high-energy milling systems have the potential to deliver more homogeneous mixtures and better electrochemical performance, but with higher costs and maintenance requirements. Therefore, the use of BMMs should be carefully optimized according to material properties and production targets.

2.1.3. Ultrasonic Mixers

Ultrasonic mixing is a technique that allows the treatment of liquid media by high-frequency sound waves in order to produce homogeneous mixtures [94]. Typically, ultrasonic mixers (USMs) are constituted by a tank or container with the slurry and an ultrasonic probe attached to an ultrasonic transducer (Figure 5). USMs promote compression and expansion cycles in the slurry through the conversion of alternating current into ultrasonic vibrations [95]. During the compression-expansion cycles, micro-scale bubbles are formed in the slurry and these bubbles grow in low-pressure half-cycles of the sound wave and collapse rapidly when they reach a certain size. This rapid collapse is named acoustic cavitation, which emits a large amount of energy through shock waves into the slurry. The released energy allows the slurry to mix at the micro level and disperse particle clusters [96]. In general, low-frequency ultrasound waves (20 kHz) are used for more effective ultrasonic mixing processes since this frequency range provides the most suitable conditions for acoustic cavitation [97]. During cavitation, bubbles undergo large pressure and temperature gradients. This leads to intense micro-turbulence that helps to attain a homogeneous mixture even in highly viscous mixtures [98]. Besides, USMs generally consume lower energy compared to HSM-based mixing methods [99].

Some key factors affect the efficiency of USM applications. Among them, the first one is the ultrasound intensity, which determines the rate of formation and the collapse force of the cavitation bubbles [100]. The high temperature and local pressure produced in the cavitation bubble collapse may improve particle dispersion; it has been reported that high densities may degrade some polymeric material [98,101]. This is particularly important for polymeric binders used in electrode production. Besides, ultrasound frequency and liquid flow are other important variables. Application of low frequencies is particularly useful for creating high-concentration slurries because cavitation bubbles are more effectively generated at these level frequencies [102]. The preparation of a high-concentration slurry saves the cost by reducing the amount of solvent used and shortens the drying time. Furthermore, since the ultrasound intensity is not distributed equally at every point in the working volume, a macro-scale liquid flow forms in the mixture. This flow causes a liquid movement towards areas where the cavitation bubbles are at lower density, which contributes to homogeneous distribution [48,103].

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of ultrasonic mixer and bubble formation and collapse mechanisms during mixing

USMs have various application areas used to ensure homogeneous mixing of different materials. The most common of these is the preparation of high-concentration slurries. Compared to traditional HSM-based methods, USMs provide better dispersion with lower energy consumption and reduce solvent usage [104,105]. In this method, particle clusters are dispersed, microturbulence is created and slurry can be prepared with lower solvent content with the help of mechanisms such as acoustic cavitation and acoustic flow [102]. Ultrasonic mixing has also attracted great interest because it is compatible with high-performance CAs such as CNT [106,107]. This application offers great advantages, especially in the development of energy storage systems. However, the scalability of USMs is still restricted because it is difficult to provide tanks appropriate for high-power systems and to adequately spread the cavitation intensity in large tanks [94]. Therefore, sufficient technological developments have not yet been made to transfer the advantages of USMs to larger volumes.

USMs play an important role in the slurry preparation step of LIB production. One of the main advantages of using a USM is the finer dispersion of particle agglomerates and the ability to produce highly concentrated slurries with low amount of solvent usage [108,109]. The production of electrodes with low solvent content reduces energy costs and increases production efficiency by shortening the drying time. At the same time, increased slurry concentration positively influences electrode quality due to the fact that shorter drying times ensure homogeneous distribution of the AM, CA, and binder, promoting a more uniform distribution of Li-ions within the electrode layer [110–112]. On the other hand, the application of high-intensity ultrasound may develop negative impacts on some kinds of polymer binders. For instance, some breakages of the polymer chains are possible during the ultrasonic treatment, which will lead to further weakening of electrochemical characteristics in the produced electrodes. Binders such as methyl cellulose and polyvinyl alcohol in particular are at risk of de-polymerization under the high-energy cavitation effect of USMs [113–115]. These degradations may lead to increased waste generation, with

affected electrode batches potentially needing to be discarded or remanufactured. Such waste not only impacts sustainability but also contributes to higher production costs. Therefore, the ultrasonic mixing method may not be applicable for slurries involving certain binders.

Chida et al. prepared $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Br}$ -coated NMC111 with vapor grown carbon fiber cathodes using ultrasonication process (100W, Shimadzu RIKA, Japan) [116]. In the study, Li_2S , P_2S_5 , and LiBr powders were ultrasonicated in ethyl propionate at 60 °C for 1h at 28 kHz with certain molar ratios to produce $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Br}$. The results obtained demonstrated that the ultrasonic homogenization method was effective in the proper distribution of the particles, creating large contact surfaces on the produced cathode. In addition, the prepared composite electrodes provided a capacity of 109 mAh/g in the first discharge cycle and the capacity retention rate was observed to be approximately 80% after ten cycles.

In the study of Vidal et al., the influence of the different compositions (both with and without Teflon[®]) and different sonication operating factors were investigated by producing LNMO-based cathodes [117]. In some cases, the slurries were prepared by using sonication for 25 min and then stirred for 48 h, while in other cases slurries were prepared by stirring for 48 h without sonication. According to the results, at 5C charge/discharge rate, sonicated electrodes showed 75% normalized discharge capacity, compared to 58% for those without sonication. This improved behavior was justified by the fact that increase in the homogeneity of the distribution of ingredients due to the sonication effect while preserving the structure of the AM.

Mori et al. investigated the influence of particle distribution of slurries on the electrode properties [118]. LCO-based slurries were prepared by hand mixing using a glass rod, ultrasonic homogenizer (US-150T, Hissei Corp., Japan) at a frequency of 20 kHz and power of 150 W, and high-speed agitator at varying rotation speeds. The obtained results showed that the application of USM provided better dispersion of acetylene black particles, leading to 10% lower density cathodes and a 15% higher volumetric resistivity of the slurry.

In the research conducted by Komoda et al., CMC adsorption behavior was studied to improve electrical conductivity and optimize battery performance by ensuring homogeneous CNT distribution in the anode structure [119]. Diluted CMC solution was premixed with CNTs using a planetary centrifugal mixer (ARE-310, Thinky Corp, Japan). Then, the mixture was dispersed for 2 h using an ultrasonic homogenizer (UX-300, Mitsui & Co, Japan) combined with a bottom shaker, operating at 20 kHz and 10-40 W to ensure homogeneous sonication. The results revealed that 95% adsorption rate was realized at an ultrasonic power of 20 W and above, which resulted in low viscosity with high electrical conductivity that ensured effective dispersion of CNTs.

USM is commonly used in different application fields such as high concentration slurry preparation, homogeneous distribution of additives in energy storage systems and low solvent usage. The major advantages of USM include low energy consumption, highly efficient mixing, micro-dispersion of particle clusters and achieving uniform mixtures through micro-turbulent effect. In particular, by providing slurries with lower solvent content and by allowing better distribution of particles in electrode structures during LIB production, thus increasing production efficiency and shortening the drying time of electrodes. This allows homogeneous distribution of

AM, CA and binder components in the electrode layer, contributing to a more even distribution of Li-ions in the electrode. However, it should be considered that high-intensity ultrasound waves may cause structural disruption of certain polymeric binders and may cause de-polymerization of some polymeric binders. Besides, there are still some limitations on USM scalability; it is difficult to provide sufficient cavitation intensity in large volumes. USM has significant potential in the field of LIB production concerning efficiency, energy saving, and performance optimization but needs more technological development up to scalability and durability of some connectors.

2.1.4. Extruder

An extruder is an equipment used primarily to homogeneously mix materials and/or shape them according to a specific profile, especially in various industries such as plastics, food, pharmaceuticals and more recently LIB production. In this process, the starting materials are fed from the hopper into the throat and then mixed and moved through the rotating screw(s) under a specific pressure and temperature. As the screw(s) rotate, the ingredients are compressed under high pressure combined with the thermal process, allowing the material to attain a liquid or semi-liquid form [120–122]. In addition, screws in extruders consist of three different zones: feeding, compression, and metering zones, respectively (Figure 6a). In the feeding section, the ingredients are conveyed from the hopper and the channel depth of the screw is wider than other sections. The compression zone is the section where the materials are mixed (melted depending on the material characteristics) and their displacement is provided by the applied temperature and the shear forces generated by the movement of the screw(s). In the final section, the metering zone, homogeneously mixed blend comes out of the extruder at a certain speed [123].

Temperature, processing time, feed rate and shear rate are important parameters of extruder applications and directly affect the final product [124]. Besides, extruders have two main categories as single-screw and twin-screw extruders, and the applied parameters change with respect to the type of extruder. Single-screw extruders have a simpler design and are generally preferred for mixing and bonding via chemical reaction of materials [49]. On the other hand, twin screw extruders are preferred especially for difficult-to-feed or thermally sensitive materials [125]. The screws in such types of extruders are placed parallel to each other and can rotate either in the same direction (co-rotating) or the opposite direction (counter-rotating), as shown in Figure 6b. Co-rotating screws provide better mixing, however; counter-rotating screws are effective in applying high pressure [126].

Figure 6. Schematic illustration of **a)** extruder and extruder zones, and **b)** different screw configurations

Extruders can be used in electrode production for the mixing step. Twin-screw extruders offer the possibility of controlling the mixing level during the process with their continuous mixing feature and segmented screw structure, and at the same time ensure that the slurry is prepared homogeneously. This process ensures that the electrode materials are mixed in the desired proportions and that sufficient shearing effect is applied to each component. In addition, each screw section can be arranged to perform a different function, thus optimizing the distribution quality of the slurry [21]. Features such as low volume processing capability, high product consistency and less waste make extruders attractive, especially for LIB production. As an advantage of the continuous mixing system, all processed materials are subjected to a certain level of shear, which increases product quality. Furthermore, low quantity material processing offers a more consistent process as well as reduces the amount of waste material by providing the possibility to intervene if any problems occur. Nevertheless, extruders have some drawbacks including the complexity of the processing, especially for high-viscosity mixtures, and the consequent difficulty in correctly setting the operation parameters of the equipment [63]. Regarding the effect of using an extruder on the mixing stage of LIB production, the viscosity of the mixture can be adjusted by the correct feed rate and appropriate screw speed settings. Features like these are some of the factors that have a direct influence on the performance of the produced battery. Incorrect feed or screw speed can negatively affect the viscosity of the slurry and reduce the performance of the produced electrode [127].

Seeba et al. aimed to develop an extrusion-based process for high-load NMC 622-based electrode production [128]. In the study, a twin-screw extruder (KETSE 20/40D, Brabender, Germany) was used for mixing with extruding speed of 40 rpm and resulting torque between 15 and 20 N/m. The produced mixtures showed acceptable processability and a trace amount of crushed NMC622 particles. In addition, when compared to traditional tape casting methods, extruded electrodes exhibited better uniformity and a negligible tendency for binder migration during rapid drying techniques, all while achieving comparable electrochemical performance. Moreover, it was stated that the drying time of electrodes produced by the extrusion method can be reduced by more than 50% compared to traditional methods.

Haarmann et al. studied the effects of different parameters applied in the extrusion process on NMC622-based slurry with the aim of reducing the quantity of solvent [129]. In the study, a continuously running co-rotating twin-screw extruder (ZSK 18, Coperion, Germany) was used for slurry preparation at a screw speed of 1200 rpm. The electrode containing solid content of 70-75% showed the highest initial charge/discharge capacities and the lowest capacity loss. Besides, increasing solid content from 65% to 75% resulted in a 40% enhancement in drying speed, resulting in an estimated 12% reduction in drying energy costs.

Borzutzki et al. investigated the effects of first kneading concentration (KC1) on the rheological behavior and electrochemical performance of graphite-based electrode pastes prepared using a twin-screw extruder (BCTM30, Bühler Group, Switzerland) [130]. According to the results, although increasing KC1 initially decreased viscosity, it increased again beyond a threshold. In addition, above a certain KC1, graphite transformed from hexagonal to rhombohedral structure. Although the intercalation mechanism remained unaffected, the enlarged surface area

promoted electrolyte decomposition and SEI growth. Accordingly, poor long-term cycling stability and low first-cycle CE were observed in the tested cells. Additionally, the authors stated that extruder operating parameters, especially engine power, show strong correlations with electrode characteristics and can serve as reliable in-line indicators for process control.

Dreger et al. researched the effects of three different mixing methods, namely dissolver (Dispermat CA, VMA-Getzmann, Germany), kneader (IKA HKD-T 0.6, IKA, Germany) and extruder (ZSK 18, Coperion, Germany), on the structural and electrochemical properties of NMC111-based slurries with low solvent content [111]. The obtained results revealed that extruded electrodes exhibited similar performances to those kneaded electrodes, especially at high C rates. The high electrochemical performance of the extruded electrode was attributed to better CB deagglomeration and nearly complete AM particle coating. Long-term cycling (200 cycles) showed the most stable performance for extruded electrodes at 60%, while higher electrical conductivity resulted from improved CB dispersion and optimized electron transport.

In conclusion, extruders play a critical role in modern industries including LIB production, enabling uniform mixing of materials and processing in specific ways. The extruder is an important candidate for electrode production with its superior advantages such as continuous processing, low waste and high product consistency, enabling homogeneous distribution of electrode materials, prevention of binder migration and, in particular, reduction of drying times due to low solvent usage. Furthermore, analyzing extruder usage in electrode production resulted in superior electrochemical properties with high specific capacity, long cycle life and high charging efficiency. However, properly adjusting the operation parameters for mixing high viscosity slurries, the damaging risk for sensitive materials and the need for higher power on industrial scale manufacturing are the downsides and limitations of extruders for use in LIB production.

2.1.5. Comparison of Mixing Equipment

Since slurry mixing is a critical step in LIB production, it has a direct impact on key slurry characteristics such as homogeneity, viscosity, and particle dispersion. These properties strongly influence electrode performance and overall cell quality. For this reason, the selection of appropriate mixing equipment becomes a crucial consideration, as the different types of mixers vary significantly in their ability to achieve the targeted slurry properties. This section provides a summary table of the mixers discussed earlier in the chapter. **Table 1** presents their advantages and disadvantages, technological maturity within the battery industry, and the production scales at which they are applied.

Table 1. Comparison of advantages and disadvantages of mixing equipment

	Advantages	Disadvantages	Maturity level	Production scale
Hydrodynamic Shear Mixers	High efficiency Mature technology Compatible parts Operable at all scales Less air bubble formation	Damage risk for binders Liquid media requirement Particle size limitations	★★★	IS PS LS
Ball Mill Mixers	Dry and wet routes Mature technology Controlled particle size reduction Compatible parts Simple equipment Mechanochemical transformation	Damage risk for solvents Contamination risk Long mixing time	★★	PS LS
Ultrasonic Mixers	High concentration slurries External stirring free design Lower energy consumption Shorter drying time	Damage risk for binders Limitations for scalability	★	LS
Extruders	Continuous processing Faster processing Same level of shear stress application Low waste High product consistency Shorter drying time	Complicated process High number of parameters High power demand for industrial scale application	★	LS

★★★: High; ★★: Moderate; ★: Low; IS: industrial-scale; PS: pilot-scale; LS: laboratory-scale

2.2. Coating

In the coating step, the prepared electrode mixture is coated with a specified thickness onto the current collectors, i.e. Al foil for positive electrodes and Cu foil for negative electrodes, using a coating machine. The electrode coating process can be applied either continuously or intermittently depending on the cell design, targeted efficiency, applied calendaring technology, and waste management strategy [28]. Moreover, coating can be processed either in wet or dry routes. For wet coating, which is preferred in industrial-scale production, a liquid organic solvent or water is used during the mixing step and due to the liquid content, a drying process should be followed, which consumes high energy. On the other side, in the dry route, mixing process is performed in a solvent-free medium and this creates the advantage of eliminating the drying step [131]. Comparing both routes, the wet-based process presents high coating speeds (20-60 m/min) while the dry-based process offers reduced production cost via eliminating the drying step, and thick electrodes with higher cell energy density. Low maturity level and low coating speeds are the main drawbacks of dry coating methods for industrial-scale applications [32,132].

The coating process is one of the most important steps of electrode production with a significant impact on the final microstructure of electrodes. Therefore, selection of the coating machine and applying appropriate coating parameters are essential to obtain desirable electrodes. The structural characteristics and the application limitations of the selected coating equipment directly influence the electrode quality and electrochemical performance. In this section, we

discussed and evaluated the most common and developing coating equipment for different application scales.

2.2.1. Slot Die Coater

Slot die coater is the most common coating machine in industrial-scale LIB production. In the slot die coating, slot die head is placed with a certain gap above the coating surface which moves continuously and in a single direction. A hydraulic pump delivers the prepared electrode slurry at a certain flow rate through the slot die head reservoir to the uncoated current collector (Figure 7a). During the coating process, electrode slurry creates an upstream and downstream meniscus between the head lips and the coating surface (Figure 7b) [33]. The coating thickness is controlled based on the flow rate of the pumped slurry and the line speed of the moving coating surface [133]. In industrial-scale manufacturing, coating and drying processes are connected through a roll-to-roll (R2R) system. The wet electrode is delivered to the dryer immediately after the coating step to evaporate the solvent in the R2R configuration. In the case of toxic and expensive NMP solvent use during the slurry preparation, the solvent is collected by evaporation process and recovered by distillation for reuse [44,134]. Moreover, the working range of slot die coaters utilized in mass production can reach up to 1400 mm in width and a coating speed of 100 m/min [32].

Line speed, slurry flow rate and viscosity, coating gap, and web tension are the main operating parameters of slot die coating process [135]. The coating speed refers to the line speed of the metallic foil to be coated passes under the slot die head. The correlation between coating speed and flow rate not only determines the coating thickness but also affects the coating quality. In the case of low line speeds with a constant flow rate, the upstream meniscus moves against the coating direction and as a result, leakage occurs. Besides, at high line speeds, the meniscus moves backward until it reaches the slot die head reservoir, and various coating defects such as air entrainment may occur, resulting in microstructural defects [136]. Moreover, if the flow rate is too low while the line speed is constant, the liquid pushed out of the head reservoir cannot provide a stable liquid bridge across the foil, and single drops or rivulets are formed on the coating surface. On the other hand, when the line speed is constant and the flow rate is too high, pressure drop occurs in the downstream coating gap, and the viscous forces within the upstream coating gap cannot be sufficient to reduce this pressure. As the upstream meniscus swells, the slurry wets the upstream die shoulder of the upstream die lip. The coating slurry spills onto the coating surface when the wetting meniscus is unable to bridge the gap [137]. In addition, web tension and line speed affect the flow rate limits. A high line speed combined with low web tension results in an increase in minimum thickness [138,139].

Figure 7. Schematic illustration of **a)** slot die coater, and **b)** cross-sectional structure of slot die head

The closed feed system characteristic of the slot die coater provides for minimizing the impact of environmental factors. In this way, it becomes easier to obtain targeted electrode properties such as capacity and defect-free surface by preserving the rheological properties of the electrode slurry and preventing environmental impurities [45]. In addition, slot die coating, as a pre-metered process, provides high consistency with controllable flow rate and adjustable coating gap and thus coating thicknesses can be preset with high tolerances and slurry lost during the process is minimized [140]. Moreover, slot die coating meets the requirements of industrial level LIB production by providing high coating speeds along with high precisions [32]. On the other hand, the slot die coating process is only applicable via wet route which necessitates the use of the toxic and environmentally hazardous NMP solvent. In addition, the need for a high-cost drying step to remove NMP increases both the overall cost of the process and the total processing time [44]. Furthermore, determining the operating parameters of the process, such as coating speed, flow rate and coating gap, to produce high-quality electrodes is a key challenge and a significantly complicated issue in slot die coating method [135]. In the case of implementation of non-optimized operating parameters, it may lead to defect formation on the electrodes such as coating cracks, pinholes, agglomerates and mud cracks [141,142]. In industrial-scale manufacturing, despite efforts to maintain homogeneous slurry mixing and filtration, agglomerates can form at the slot-die, causing coating defects and resulting in material loss and associated cost. For example, approximately 5.76 kg of AM (in the case of LFP) can become unusable due to 30 seconds of incorrectly coated electrode, corresponding to a material cost of around 115 USD for a single-layer coating [32]. Consequently, minimizing waste generation in slot-die coating requires optimization of slurry quality, effective filtration and continuous circulation to control particulates, sensor-based monitoring of process parameters, and regular equipment maintenance.

Chen et al. proposed a novel technique for improving the battery performance using a double-layered cathode produced by simultaneous slot die coating method (Figure 8) [143]. In the study, NMC532-based slurries were prepared with the same formulation but using different proportions of two different CAs, namely micro-sized graphite and nano-sized CB. For coating process, a two-layered slot die coater was used and coating width and coating speed were set at 10 cm and 1.7

cm/s, respectively. The obtained results revealed that batteries made up of two layered cathodes showed longer cycle life and high current rate performance.

Figure 8. Two-layered simultaneous slot-die coating set-up used in the study, **a)** front view, **b)** side view. Reprinted with permission from [143]

Schmitt et al. investigated the effect of slot die coating parameters on the edge formation by preparing graphite-based anodes and analyzing the edges quantitatively with a laser sensor [144]. According to the results, height and width of the superelevated coating edge were not significantly affected by coating speed within the range of around 10 to 30 m/min, but the edge gradient sharpened at higher speeds. Moreover, it was found that the area affected by the edge effect expanded toward the center of the coated surface with increasing coating gap ratio. Consequently, minimizing the coating gap can contribute to obtaining an optimal coating edge.

In the study of Chin et al., different process parameters were investigated to expand the defect-free "coating window" in slot die coating [145]. Based on the findings, low-viscosity solutions reduce minimum coating thickness and increase maximum coating speed. In addition, rear-neck geometry delays defects to higher speeds and allows thicker coatings, while front-neck geometry creates a smaller window with thinner, more uniform coatings. Moreover, increasing the backward incline of the die decreases minimum thickness and shifts the window to higher speeds, whereas forward incline increases minimum thickness and expands the window to higher flow rates. The combination front-neck geometry with backward incline yields the thinnest layer at high speeds, representing the most effective way to achieve a thin, homogeneous coating without extra equipment.

To sum up, slot die coating is a mature and industrially adopted method in LIB manufacturing. The advantages of a pre-metered process and adjustable operating parameters allow for more precise and controllable electrode production. Moreover, isolated feeding system prevents prepared slurry against environmental impurities and rheological degradations. On the other hand, the large number of operating parameters and the need for accurate combinations of parameters make this method complex. In addition, the necessity of the wet route requires the use of some toxic organic solvents and the application of a drying step.

2.2.2. Doctor Blade Coater

Doctor blade coating, also known as tape casting, is a conventional coating technique that is mostly used in laboratory-scale LIB research. During the application, blade set-up is positioned on the top of the current collector with the specified coating gap. Following the placement of the prepared electrode slurry in front of the blade either manually or by a pump, a constant relative motion is applied between the blade and the foil. As a result, the slurry is coated onto the foil as a wet layer with the specified thickness (Figure 9) [146]. Furthermore, the coating process can be performed by the movement of the blade while the coating surface is kept stationary, or by keeping the blade fixed and moving the coating surface, similar to the slot die coater operation. In this technique, the coating gap typically varies from twenty to several hundred microns and the coating speed is up to several meters per minute [147].

Unlike slot die coater, doctor blade is a self-metered system, meaning variables such as blade angle, coating width and blade pressure on the coating surface are already calibrated for optimum process efficiency [33,148]. Apart from the slurry viscosity, one of the most important parameters is the coating gap, which expresses the distance between the blade and the coating surface and determines the coating thickness. In addition, the meniscus formed by the slurry between the blade and the coating surface, as well as the slurry concentration, also affects coating thickness. Besides, the meniscus is controlled by the coating gap, the speed of the moving part relative to the other (blade to coating surface or coating surface to the blade), the slurry viscosity, and the blade geometry [33]. Non-optimized slurry viscosity, high coating speeds and improper placement of the slurry can lead to various defects in the doctor blade coating process, such as inhomogeneous coating layer and slurry leakage [149].

Figure 9. Schematic illustration of doctor blade coater and tape casting process

The self-calibrated characteristic of doctor blade coater and its relatively low number of operational parameters make it a user-friendly method. In addition to this, its low CAPEX and

high OPEX, combined with its easy-to-use feature, are among the primary reasons for its frequent use in laboratory research [149]. Moreover, with similarities to the slot die coater, its high consistency and repeatability allow it to be easily scalable. Approximately 5% of the coating material may be lost during the application of the method; however, this loss can be minimized through the implementation of optimized parameters [150]. On the other hand, after each process, the need to reposition an uncoated foil and the blade setup for the next coating, reflecting its lack of continuity, and along with the limited coating area (10-20 cm²), makes this method inefficient in terms of time. Additionally, open reservoir design of the doctor blade coater exposes the electrode slurry to the risk of environmental factors. As with the slot die coater, the necessity of the wet route application is a drawback both economically and environmentally.

In their research, Du et al. conducted a study to eliminate the difficulties of metallic Li coating on lithiophobic Cu foil [151]. After sputtering a Sn nanolayer onto Cu foil to create a lithiophilic interface, molten Li was spread onto the Cu/Sn substrate using a doctor blade coater. The authors demonstrated that this approach is highly suitable for industrial-scale production, as Li/Li-Sn electrodes showed stable cycling performance for 900 h and exhibited exceptional flexibility and mechanical strength.

Hasanpoor et al. investigated the effects of coating of high purity Al with different particle sizes, coating techniques and calendaring processes on the performance of the separators [152]. Al particles were coated by using three different coaters which are doctor blade coater with a 120 μm coating gap, spin coater, and electrospin coater. According to the results, it was observed that the doctor blade method provided the most homogeneous coating with an average coating thickness of 38 μm . In addition, according to the bend and crosshatch adhesion test results, doctor blade coated separators showed the best mechanical performance with the strongest bond to the substrate as well as the highest resistance to scratching, cracking and peeling.

In the study of Adityarini et al., the effects of different LFP cathode thicknesses on the electrochemical performances were investigated [153]. In the production step, the prepared LFP-based cathode slurry was coated on the Al foils using a doctor blade coater with thickness of 150, 200, 250 and 300 μm . As a result of the analysis, the minimum degradation level was observed in the cathode with the thickness of 250 μm , while the electrode with the thickness of 300 μm showed the highest degradation level due to the breakage caused by high coating thickness.

In conclusion, the doctor blade coater is a widely preferred coating equipment in laboratory-scale LIB research due to its low maintenance and investment cost and ease to operate. Its features of providing homogeneous coating, repeatability, and adjustable coating gaps not only make this equipment suitable for laboratory-scale research but also position it as a strong candidate for large-scale production. Although being a self-metered equipment provides the advantage of low operational limits, non-optimized process parameters hinder an appropriate coating process. In addition, being a wet route technique is one of the most important obstacles to become a more economical method while the open reservoir feature poses a critical risk in terms of contamination.

2.2.3. Comma Bar Coater

The comma bar coater is a coating system that combines the features of a fixed blade system with a R2R configuration [154]. It can be described as a scaled-up version of the doctor blade technique, both at pilot and industrial levels, featuring a self-calibrated mechanism where the volume of slurry applied is determined by the coating gap [155]. In this system, prepared electrode slurry is fed into an open reservoir and transferred from a comma-shaped blade featuring a curved front edge to backing roll, then moved to the current collector located on the bump roll to be coated (Figure 10). In addition, web speed and wet coating thickness, as well as coating gap and distance between backing and bump rolls, are critical parameters that directly affect process efficiency and final electrode quality [156].

Román-Ramírez et al. investigated the effect of coating and drying process parameters on the physical and electrochemical properties of NMC622-based electrodes prepared with a comma bar coater [157]. The authors stated that comma bar coating gap and coating ratio are the main parameters affecting gravimetric and volumetric capacity and rate performance. In addition, it was emphasized that the formulation and distribution effects are directly reflected in the final cell performance by the amount of coated slurry and therefore, coating gap and ratio are critical parameters to optimize battery performance in comma bar coater application.

In brief, comma bar coater is a self-metered blade coating machine. Coating gap, coating speed and coating ratio are the basic parameters that directly affect the electrode manufacturing process, therefore the battery performance, and must be carefully determined. Comma bar coater can be used effectively in pilot-level research and production processes and find application in this context; however, slot die coaters are generally preferred at the industrial level electrode production.

Figure 10. Schematic illustration of comma bar coater and coating process

2.2.4. Dry Coating Machinery

In the dry route coating methods, electrode mixtures are prepared with dry particles instead of adding solvents such as water and organic solvents. In the last few years, dry coating methods have

gained popularity in the LIB manufacturing industry, particularly since Tesla acquired Maxwell Technology Inc. in 2019 with the intention of utilizing this technology to produce batteries of the future [131]. Eliminating the use of solvents reduces both consumable costs and the drying stage, providing approximately 47% energy savings and a 19% reduction in production costs as well as shorter production times [32]. In addition to cost-effectiveness, solvent-free methods allow for thick electrode production, which is a challenge for traditional wet coating methods, resulting in higher cell energy density. On the other hand, uniformity, scale-up challenges and mechanical stability are the main drawbacks of the dry coating concept [44].

2.2.4.1. Dry Calendering via Rolling Press

The rolling press is used mainly during the calendering step in LIB production to enhance the compactness of coated electrodes and to adjust porosity and thickness, which will be discussed in detail in a later section. Free standing electrode fabrication (FSEF) and direct calendering are two similar manufacturing methods. Both methods provide dry coating by means of rolling press. In both methods, dry powder mixture is directly fed into counter-rotating rollers to be compressed by applied shear forces and create electrode films. In the FSEF technique, fabricated electrodes are pressed onto the current collectors using an external laminating roll (Figure 11a). Whereas in the direct calendering process, the powder mixture is directly applied onto the current collector without using an external roller (Figure 11b) [158].

Figure 11. Schematic illustration of **a)** Free standing electrode fabrication, **b)** Direct calendering

The distance and rotation ratio between the rolls determine the intensity of the applied shear forces. Besides, from the characteristics point of view of the rolls, such as surface, morphology, the material it is made from and diameter, are directly related to the internal friction between the particles. Additionally, angles of the roll gap affect the applied pressure on the fed particles. Apart from the roll properties, the shear force is also dependent on the mixture characteristics such as the composition of the mixture, particle size and distribution, and powder morphology. During the process, shear forces need to be carefully controlled to avoid failures such as rupturing, swelling as well as edge distortion. Moreover, maximizing the feed zone and minimizing the nip zone simultaneously allows to production of electrodes with higher porosity, lower thickness and

homogeneous density distribution. This arrangement promotes uniform powder distribution due to increased shear zone and therefore allows the manufacturing of mechanically more stable electrodes by applying only the required compaction level [159].

The FSEF and direct calendaring methods are rather mature technologies with relatively high technological readiness levels (TRL), with FSEF at TRL6 and direct calendaring at TRL5 which make them ready to industrial deployment. In addition, being continuous methods and capable of producing electrodes with quality comparable to conventional wet coating methods, along with the elimination of the drying process and solvent usage leading to cost reduction, make them strong candidates for industrial applications. On the other hand, the necessity of the lamination process in the FSEF process and the fact that it is a significant challenge to reach high coating speeds constitutes an obstacle for this method to reach its potential. In contrast, a significant advantage of direct calendaring lies in its potential for high coating speeds, reaching up to 100 m/min, which can even surpass those of the conventional wet chemical coating processes. However, in direct calendaring, the difficulty of finding the right binder in anode production limits this application [158]. Furthermore, during dry calendaring processes, waste generation primarily arises from material handling and processing inconsistencies. Uneven distribution, misalignment, or improper compression of the electrode material can lead to local defects or broken edges, while particle entrapment or surface irregularities may cause layer delamination and material loss. Although this approach avoids solvent-related waste and allows precise control of electrode thickness and density, careful monitoring and equipment maintenance are essential to minimize scrap and ensure consistent production quality.

Maxwell Technology has made significant progress in dry coating technology by integrating the dry coating technique they already use in ultracapacitor electrode production using FSEF into LIB electrode manufacturing [160]. They summarize their study in three solvent-free steps: mixing dry powders, powder to film formation, and laminating the film onto the current collector, respectively. They claimed that the developed dry electrode production method can be integrated into both traditional and advanced battery materials and is industrially scalable to R2R production configuration. In addition, DRYtraec[®] is a direct calendaring machine developed and patented by Fraunhofer IWS [161]. This novel machine provides LIB electrode fabrication without any use of solvent. Thus, it is both ecologically friendly and economical. It supports the advances in dry coating technology, from laboratory-scale research for new battery technologies to industrial prototype development for process and equipment optimization. It also offers continuous and simultaneous double-sided coating with a four-roll system.

In summary, dry calendaring methods are promising methods for industrial-scale dry electrode production. Their working principles are mainly based on the pressing of dry powder mixtures using a rolling press and subsequent dry coating on current collectors. The efficiency of the coating process is dependent on the properties of the roller, the supplied powder mixture characteristics, and consequently, the applied pressure and the rotational speed of the rollers. Besides the cost reduction advantage, high maturity and ability to produce an acceptable electrode quality make them attractive in LIB production. However, their application potentials are currently restricted due to the limited binder options and challenges in industrial integration.

2.2.4.2. Electrostatic Spray Deposition

Electrostatic spray deposition (ESD) is a popular solvent-free coating method. The working principle of ESD is based on spraying of charged dry electrode mixture particles to the current collector. In the first step, fluidized dry electrode particles are charged by spray gun to create a potential difference between the gun and the ground current collector. After this, the charged dry electrode mixture is carried from the spray gun to the coating surface through electrostatic forces induced by the generated voltage (Figure 12) [162]. In the final stage, the sprayed electrode is moved to a hot roller to thermally activate and consolidate the binder, ensuring adequate adhesion and cohesion between the sprayed particles and current collectors [131].

In the ESD process, coating is controlled by a range of parameters such as applied charging voltage and coating gap between the spray gun tip and ground current collector. In the case of the low charging voltage, the particles may not be charged and are prevented from reaching the coating surface evenly, resulting in inhomogeneous coating. Conversely, if overcharging voltage is applied, a strong electric field is generated between the spray gun and the current collector, and when the electric field strength is large enough, the air is dissociated, causing a short circuit or even damage to the equipment. In addition, in cases where particles cannot be easily charged, the coating gap plays an important role. Reducing the gap can make the deposition process easier; however, excessively narrowing the gap may cause uneven particle deposition and a reduction in the spray area [163]. Moreover, the thickness and density of the final electrode are controlled by applied pressure during hot rolling [164].

Figure 12. Schematic illustration of electrostatic spray deposition

The ESD method offers numerous advantages, such as the ability to dry route electrode coatings, as well as good flexibility, cost-effective processing and capability to binder-free electrode production [165]. Additionally, it is an attractive coating equipment as it can be used for many common AMs used in LIB production [132]. On the other hand, the fact that an electrode

layer with dimensions of 18 mm x 25 mm is coated in approximately 1 minute and does not provide a continuous coating process reduces the effectiveness of this method. Another limitation of the ESD technique is the difficulty in controlling electrode thickness [166]. During ESD process, waste generation primarily arises from overspray, non-uniform deposition, and material rebound from the substrate. Particles that fail to adhere to the electrode surface or accumulate in unintended areas are lost as scrap, and localized defects may occur due to uneven coating thickness or charge distribution. While this method allows solvent-free coating and precise control over layer morphology, careful process optimization and equipment maintenance are crucial to minimize material loss and ensure consistent electrode quality.

Al-Shroofy et al. demonstrated laboratory-scale dry coated NMC111 electrode production using ESD technique with a corona-type electrostatic spray gun [166]. When dry coated electrodes and conventionally produced electrodes were compared on Li half cells, the results showed that the discharge capacity of dry coated electrodes was slightly lower than the conventional ones. In addition, the ESD'ed electrode outperforms the conventional slurry coated electrode in terms of cycling performance due to its improved capacity retention and stable performance.

In the study of Guo et al., dual-layer NMC811-based solvent-free electrodes were produced by the ESD method under an applied voltage of 25 kV [167]. According to the results, the electrodes fabricated by the ESD method demonstrated remarkable improvements over commercial slurry-cast electrodes, including a 14% increase in discharge-specific capacity, enhanced rate capability and 14% higher long-term cycling stability. On the other hand, the authors stated that despite these advancements, critical challenges such as capacity fading and electrode detachment under high-loading conditions still remain, necessitating further optimization of electrode design and manufacturing protocols.

Ludwig et al. reported a novel solvent-free LIB electrode manufacturing process [168]. In the study, LCO-based electrodes were coated using the ESD method with an applied voltage of 25 kV, followed by a hot rolling process for thermal activation of the used binder. According to the obtained results, the bonding performance of hot rolled electrodes was significantly higher (148.8 kPa) than that of the original dry coated electrodes (1.2 kPa) and the conventional slurry-cast method (84.3 kPa). Furthermore, the half cells containing ESD'ed electrodes exhibited slightly higher capacity and cycling stability as compared to the half cells made of conventional electrodes.

To sum up, ESD is an attractive and under development dry coating machinery for LIB research due to its superior advantages such as being cost-effective and applicable for common LIB active materials. In addition, conducted studies show that hot rolling process applied following deposition increases the bonding performance of the electrode particles and ESD'ed electrodes perform higher cycling performance and reliability compared to traditional wet slurry coating methods. However, electrode thickness control and relatively low time efficiency are challenges that need to be overcome to increase the scalability of this method. In the ESD method, the set potential difference, the working distance between the gun tip and the coating surface and the applied hot rolling parameters directly determine the coating quality and electrode performance.

2.2.5. Comparison of Coating Equipment

Slurry coating is a key step that directly determines the electrode quality and, consequently, the performance of the battery. The effectiveness of this step heavily depends on the selected coating equipment, since each technique introduces unique challenges and capabilities that influence the final electrode quality. In this section, a summary table provides a concise overview of the coating equipment investigated in the previous parts of this chapter. **Table 2** outlines the advantages and disadvantages of each equipment, their maturity levels within LIB production, and the scales of production where they are typically utilized.

Table 2. Comparison of advantages and disadvantages of coating equipment

	Advantages	Disadvantages	Maturity Level	Production Scale
Slot Die Coater	Isolated feed system High consistency Mature technology Controllable electrode production	High number of parameters Solvent usage requirement	★★★	IS PS
Doctor Blade Coater	Self-calibrated High consistency Mature technology Easy-to-use Cost-effective	Non-continuous Limited coating area Open reservoir design Solvent usage requirement	★★★	LS
Comma Bar Coater	Self-calibrated Continuous processing	Open reservoir design Solvent usage requirement	★★★	IS PS
Dry Calendering via Rolling Press	Solvent-free coating Cost saving Continuous High TRL	Low coating speed (FSEF) Binder limitation (Direct calendering) Industrial integration challenges	★★	PS LS
Electrostatic Spray Deposition	Solvent-free coating Cost saving Flexible electrode production Binder-free production	Non-continuous Limited coating area Thickness control difficulty	★	LS

★★★: High; ★★: Moderate; ★: Low; IS: industrial-scale; PS: pilot-scale; LS: laboratory-scale

2.3. Drying

After slurry coating, the solvent content in the electrodes must be removed which is not required for dry coated electrodes as mentioned in the previous section. In industrial level production, coating and drying lines are often connected by an R2R system, which means that the coated electrodes continue to move directly from the coater to the dryer to evaporate the solvent [169]. In many applications, the toxic and expensive NMP solvent is evaporated and then recovered using a condenser, also called the solvent recovery process. Drying and solvent recovery processes represent the highest energy consumption steps, accounting for 46.8% of all production [44,170].

In drying process, as solvent molecules evaporate along the coated area, they drag the other components of the electrode (AM, CA and binder) and lead to rearrangement of particles included in the coating. Therefore, drying process has a critical impact on the final microstructural and electrochemical characteristics of the electrode [171]. In addition, drying is a complex process due to the fact that it is affected by many factors such as features of the slurry (sedimentation and diffusion characteristics of the particles, flow properties, solid to liquid ratio, binder type etc.), characteristics of the solvent to be evaporated (viscosity, boiling point, evaporation rate etc.) [39,172]. Moreover, when operating the dryer, six key parameters that directly impact the drying process must be considered: the drying method, drying regime, roll speed, applied drying temperature, hot air velocity, and energy consumption [45]. As a consequence of non-optimized drying conditions, defects such as binder and/or CA migration, component segregation and electrode curling, crack or delamination may occur, leading to reduced electrode quality and performance [173]. In this part, the focus is on discussing and assessing the commonly used and advancing drying technologies in LIB manufacturing.

2.3.1. Hot Air Convective Dryer

Hot air convective dryer is the state-of-the-art machine used in both pilot and industrial level LIB production. In this method, the wet coated electrode is exposed to hot air flow to evaporate the solvent content (Figure 13) [174]. In the first stage, evaporation of solvent from the top surface of the coating causes shrinkage in the electrode. This process continues until the hard AM particles come into contact with each other, at which point the decrease in film thickness stops. In the second stage, the solvent in the pores between the AM particles evaporates. The solvent molecules diffuse through the thickness of the electrode, causing displacement of other electrode components and reshaping of the microstructure [45,175]. While dryers in industrial-scale production consist of more than one drying chamber, in laboratory-scale research the drying process is carried out in a single segment with no air flow and generally in a vacuum drying oven [176–178]. In industrial level production, dryers typically have a tunnel configuration consisting of multiple chambers, each operating at different temperatures and dwelling times [162]. In general, to increase the efficiency of dryers, the temperatures of the three-stage chambers are usually set in a low-moderate-high pattern, with a dwelling time of 1-2 minutes in each chamber. The first zone is usually set at 75–90°C, while the last zone reaches approximately 125–140°C [28,179]. The lengths of the chambers can be customized, as can their temperatures, but it is common to design them to be of equal length. This approach is preferred to avoid rapid drying and thermal stresses to which the electrode may be subjected. Especially at high coating speeds, when drying length is limited, air flow is provided both above and below the film surface [39,180].

Drying speed and drying rate can directly affect the mechanical properties of the electrode, leading to various defects such as cracking, curling and delamination. Therefore, optimizing the durations in the temperature zones directly affects the electrode quality. In addition, air flow density and air flow rate are important for the balanced progress of the drying process [45]. Moreover, hot air convective drying is based on a well-established and mature technology, ensuring stable production processes and delivering high-quality electrode manufacturing, making it a reliable and widely preferred choice in the LIB industry. However, long dryer design leads to inefficiency in the production area, increases the risk of wrinkling of current collector foils and

makes web tension control difficult. In addition, it creates a disadvantage in terms of sustainability by increasing operational costs due to high energy consumption [181]. Hot air convective drying often generates waste through non-uniform solvent evaporation, where variations in airflow or temperature can cause cracking, binder migration, or delamination of the electrode coating. These defects reduce usable yield and create scrap, especially in large-scale continuous operation.

Figure 13. Schematic illustration of hot air convection dryer and drying process

Jaiser et al. proposed a novel three-stage drying profile to optimize the anode drying process, aiming to reduce the total drying time while preserving the mechanical integrity of the anode layer [182]. Throughout the process, in the drying regime where hot air flow was used, a high drying rate (HDR) was applied in the first and final stages to rapidly remove the solvent, while a low drying rate (LDR) was used in the intermediate stage to prevent binder migration. The results showed that this drying technique reduced the total drying time by 40%, while significantly preserving the mechanical strength and structural integrity of the anode layer.

Hot air convective dryer is one of the advanced drying systems used in LIB production at different scales and is based on the principle of exposing wet coated electrodes to hot air flow to evaporate the solvent content. This system is usually designed in a tunnel configuration with multiple drying chambers and different temperature regimes are applied in each chamber to optimize the drying process. Drying time, air flow intensity and temperature zones are important parameters that directly affect the electrode quality and should be carefully optimized to prevent mechanical defects. At high coating speeds and limited drying areas, providing hot air flow both above and below the electrode surface is critical for the effectiveness of the drying process. While it stands out for providing high-quality and stable electrode production and is widely used in the industry, it also has disadvantages such as long dryer design leading to inefficiency in the production area and increasing operational costs due to high energy consumption.

2.3.2. Infrared Radiation Dryer

Infrared radiation (IR), located between the visible light and microwave regions in the electromagnetic spectrum, covers a wavelength range from 0.75 to 1000 μm [183]. In IR dryers,

IR emitters are heated electrically to generate electromagnetic energy waves that are to be absorbed by the electrode (Figure 14). The absorption of the emitted radiation increases molecular vibrations within the coating, causing the electrode to heat up and the solvent to evaporate [184]. In industrial-scale LIB production, the combination of hot air convection and IR drying is currently the primary focus in terms of the drying process. The main purpose of integrating IR dryers, particularly as pre-heaters, into convective dryers is to enhance energy efficiency while also reducing the dryer length and increasing web speed [181]. The efficiency of the IR drying process depends on the emitted wavelength and the absorptivity of the materials composing the electrode. Additionally, the wavelength spectrum of the emitted radiation is determined by the intrinsic properties of the emitter and the temperature applied to it [185]. Furthermore, the penetration depth of the radiation on the electrode is influenced by factors such as the electrode thickness, the structural properties of slurry components, and solvent activity [186].

Figure 14. Schematic illustration of infrared radiation dryer and drying process

IR dryers provide cost-effective drying by converting electrical energy into heat with high efficiency, long service life, low maintenance and low operating costs. In addition, it offers an effective and practical solution in the industrial-scale drying process, as the emitted radiation penetrates directly into the electrode without heating the environment and provides homogeneous heating on the electrode, occupies reduced space and can be easily adapted to previously conventional dryers. On the other hand, the scalability of IR dryers is not always a straightforward procedure, and since they are more suitable for surface drying, adapting them for the drying of thick electrodes poses a significant challenge. Furthermore, potential fire hazards must be carefully considered in both the design and operational phases [185]. Although IR dryers improve overall drying efficiency, uncoated areas being exposed to radiation can lead to rapid overheating and potential damage of the current collector. Moreover, solvent boiling defects may occur if the upper coating layers are cured before the trapped solvent in the lower layers can escape [181]. These defects ultimately generate waste material and contribute to electrode scrap.

Altwater et al. investigated the efficiency of near-infrared radiation (NIR) method in the drying process of water-based graphite anodes [187]. In the experimental section, produced electrodes were exposed to three different drying methods, namely hot air convection, NIR drying and combination of hot air convection and NIR drying. According to the results, the NIR method enhances solvent evaporation by providing the highest electrode temperatures while also ensuring the drying of electrodes with the best adhesion performance. However, it was noted that complete elimination of hot air flow could reduce drying efficiency and excessive IR radiation could cause disintegration of binders.

In summary, the IR drying method is based on heating the electrode through the absorption of electromagnetic infrared waves generated by electrically heated emitters, leading to solvent evaporation. The wavelength of and penetration depth of the emitted radiation are the key factors that determine the efficiency of the process. Being cost effective and providing homogeneous drying has increased interest in combining it with conventional drying methods in industrial applications and intensifying the studies in this field. However, adapting IR dryers for drying thick electrodes represents an obstacle, while high intensity IR radiation can cause the breakdown of binders, negatively affecting electrode quality.

2.3.3. Microwave Dryer

Microwaves (MW) are the portion of the electromagnetic spectrum between 1 mm to 1 m in wavelength, corresponding to frequencies between 300 MHz and 300 GHz [188]. In MW drying, the electrode is subjected to MW radiation from a magnetron in order to induce heating within the electrode itself by exciting polar molecules (Figure 15). Unlike other methods, direct heat flow is not in contact with the electrode instead; heating within the electrode is done through molecular excitation created by the alternating electromagnetic field [181,189,190]. Moreover, MW intensity and frequency are the two most important key parameters that need to be suitably controlled for an efficient MW drying process. In addition, the temperature profile must be properly managed to prevent the electrode components from overheating and any thermal degradation. The thermal properties of electrode materials such as thermal conductivity and heat capacity have a significant impact on the heat generation and heat transfer inside the electrode. Moreover, similar to the IR dryer, the MW dryer can be integrated into conventional dryer systems to increase overall drying efficiency [191].

Figure 15. Schematic illustration of microwave dryer and drying process

The MW dryer provides homogeneous heating from the inside out, not on the surface. This characteristic brings important advantages such as providing a faster drying process and reducing binder migration as well as increasing the internal pore diffusion rate of the solvent. In addition, the drying speed can be increased by volumetric heating of the electrode, which is an important upside, especially for thick electrodes and increased area loadings. MWs interact directly with the material, preventing unnecessary heat losses and increasing energy conversion efficiency. Besides, the compact design of MW dryers reduces floor space requirements and accelerates the production processes owing to the shortening of drying times by 50% or more. These features make the MW dryer one of the effective solutions in several industrial applications [191]. On the other hand, the reflection of MWs by metallic current collectors can cause irregular wave reflections and uneven heat distribution in the coating layer, which may damage the dryer. In addition, sudden and overheating can cause electrode burnout, internal pressure buildup, and even explosion, resulting in defective electrode layers that must be scrapped, thereby contributing to waste generation. Finally, both the equipment and operating costs of these systems can be high, which can limit their applicability on an industrial scale [188,192,193].

Peelamedu et al. proposed a novel inline hybrid MW drying system [194]. In this work, NMC532-based cathode and graphite-based anode slurries were prepared using both NMP and aqueous solutions. The electrodes were dried in the hybrid MW drying system at temperatures up to 125°C for NMP-based electrodes and up to 80°C for aqueous-based electrodes, with varying durations. The results obtained showed that the moisture level of NMP-based electrodes was significantly decreased by increasing the drying time. Conversely, the high moisture level was observed in aqueous-based electrodes, which was ascribed to the applied low drying temperature. In addition, NMP-based cathodes provided more consistent electrochemical performance with longer drying times, whereas aqueous-based electrodes exhibited performance loss at high C rates due to high moisture levels. Furthermore, as a result of microstructural investigations performed after 103 minutes of drying time, it was determined that MWs did not cause any deterioration in the electrode microstructure.

In conclusion, MW drying is an attractive drying method within the scope of LIB manufacturing for its excellent features including uniform heating, faster processing, and reduced binder migration effect. Besides that, MW drying could also be one of the competitive options in industrial production for LIB owing to its compact design, high energy conversion efficiency, and requirement shorter time for drying. However, risks such as the reflection of MWs by metallic foils and the danger of overheating pose challenges in application, so further optimization is needed for large-scale production integration.

2.3.4. Comparison of Drying Equipment

Proper drying of coated electrodes is an essential step in the LIB fabrication, as it ensures the removal of residual solvents without compromising the structural integrity of the electrode. The choice of drying equipment and process parameters critically affects the electrode quality and electrochemical performance. To provide a clear overview, this section includes a summary table of the drying techniques discussed earlier in the chapter. **Table 3** highlights each method's

advantages and disadvantages, technological maturity in industrial applications, and the production scales at which they are implemented.

Table 3. Comparison of advantages and disadvantages of drying equipment

	Advantages	Disadvantages	Maturity level	Production scale
Hot Air Convective Dryer	Mature technology High-quality electrode production Suitable for thick electrodes	Non-compact design High energy consumption High risk of binder migration	★★★	IS PS
Infrared Radiation Dryer	Compact design Cost-effective Long service life Less risk of binder migration	Poor performance for thick electrodes Scalability challenge	★★	PS LS
Microwave Dryer	Compact design Faster processing Suitable for thick electrodes Less risk of binder migration	Reflection of MWs by metallic foils High cost Underexplored	★	LS

★★★: High; ★★: Moderate; ★: Low; IS: industrial-scale; PS: pilot-scale; LS: laboratory-scale

2.4. Calendering

Calendering is the final step of electrode fabrication where the compaction of electrodes takes place. For calendering, roll press machine has been adopted from laboratory-scale research to industrial level production. The roll pressing of electrodes is based on feeding the coated electrode into the set gap between rolls rotating in opposite directions, applying a constant compressive load to the electrode as it passes through the gap by the rotating rolls (Figure 16) [162,195]. During the process, applied mechanical force enhances the compactness of the electrode particles and the adhesion between the coating and current collector, allowing a reduction in electrode thickness and porosity, and increasing in volumetric energy density [39,196]. In addition, the decrease in porosity leads to an increase in the contact points between conductive particles, strengthening the conductivity network and increasing the electrical conductivity. In contrast, since the transportation of Li-ions is provided by the electrolyte filling the pores, ionic conductivity is positively correlated with porosity [179]. Consequently, calendering has a significant impact on the electrochemical, physical and mechanical properties of the electrodes and hence on the performance of LIBs.

Figure 16. Schematic illustration of roll press and calendaring process

Since the calendaring process strongly affects the various properties of the electrodes, the characteristics and operating parameters of the roll press must be well understood. Generally, calendaring step is applied at elevated temperatures (i.e., above the glass-transition temperature of the binder) to achieve reduced resistance of porosity and compaction as well as higher adhesion strength [21,196]. Therefore, roll presses may have roll heating function which can be achieved through hot oil, electric elements or gas [197]. Another important characteristic of rolling press is the rolling pressure capacity. During calendaring, insufficient or excessive pressure applications may negatively affect the quality of electrodes and the performance of batteries. Besides, roller press machines with high pressure capacity are preferred in order to produce high energy density batteries [198]. Thus, pressure capacity is one of the key features to consider in the selection of the rolling press. In addition, roller diameter and width are crucial factors that affect the distribution of applied pressure. The use of large diameter rolls compresses the electrode material in a more controlled manner, ensuring a balanced distribution of mechanical stress, while smaller diameter rolls apply higher pressure, resulting in more aggressive compression [199]. Furthermore, considering the characteristics of the above-mentioned roll press, the roller materials are required to exhibit a series of properties such as high mechanical strength, high abrasion resistance and good thermal conductivity and thermal stability. The roll press manufacturers prefer stainless steel-based alloys plated with Cr and/or Mo to prevent corrosion in roll production [200–203].

Although the calendaring is a relatively straightforward process compared to the other electrode manufacturing steps, the operating parameters play a crucial role in the final characteristics of the electrode. For example, excessive pressure application may cause defects in the electrodes such as coating cracks, wrinkles and loss of contact between the particles [204,205]. It is important to note that the wrinkling effect can be reduced by heating the rolls [28]. Moreover, rolling speed, contact area, roll gap and applied temperature are the parameters that define the

contact duration of the electrodes with rolls, porosity and compaction resistance and spring back effect of electrodes [196]. Additionally, nonparallel operating rolls may cause irregularity in the distribution of thickness and density of the electrodes [169].

Meyer et al. investigated the impacts of heated calendering process on the porosity, compaction resistance and adhesion strength properties of NMC111-based cathodes with different composition ratios [205]. According to the results obtained, elastic deformability of the binder (PVDF) increases with increasing roll temperature and this results in decreasing in the compaction resistance of the electrode. Besides, the compaction resistance decreases with decreasing amount of additive contents. Moreover, increasing roll temperature has a positive impact on the adhesion strength of the coating.

Haselrieder et al. conducted comprehensive research on the effect of the compression rate on the microstructural and electrochemical properties of graphite-based anodes [206]. In the study, prepared electrodes were calendered at compression rates of 5, 10, 15, 20 and 26% using a pilot scale roll press (Saueressig GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Unsurprisingly, the density increased and the porosity decreased with increasing compression rate. In addition, the application of 20 and 26% compression rates resulted in the closing of the big pores of the electrodes. Moreover, 10% of compression rates exhibited the best long-term cycling performance compared to others. It was also observed that the electrodes subjected to compression rates higher than 20% showed poor long-term cycling performance. The authors stated that this result could be attributed to the decreased electrolyte wettability of the electrodes due to the blockage of large pores and hence low Li-ion transfer.

Keilhofer et al. investigated a novel mechanical electrode structuring concept by using a built-in house hand-operated embossing roll press [207]. The embossing roller used in the study basically consists of two vertically arranged rollers -one with a pattern and the other with a flat surface-, a spindle to set applied load, adjustable wedges to vary roller gap and various components such as the cover plate, the springs and bearings. In the experimental section, pyramid-like structures in a squared texture with a spacing of 220 μm were created on the surface of the graphite-based and NMC622-based electrodes by using the embossing roller. In addition, electrochemical tests results showed that discharge capacity of anode increased by up to 14.3% at 2C rate.

In this chapter, we investigated the effects and importance of the calendering step with example studies from literature and working principle, important operating parameters and characteristics of the roll press. Since the calendering process is a low-cost and low-energy consuming process, the variety of machines used in calendering and the studies conducted on the machines have remained low [44,208]. Apart from this, the roll press is a low operating cost equipment used in the calendering step of both laboratory-scale research studies and mass production. The pressure capacity, roll diameter and width characteristics, and temperature function are the features that should be taken into account when selecting the appropriate roll press machine. Besides, applied process variables such as pressure, roll temperature, rolling speed and roll gap are the parameters that directly affect final electrode quality and performance.

3. Future Trends and Challenges

While today's Gigafactory scale production is already mature, scrap rates remain high. It is important to consider that the production of commercial LIBs requires high amounts of scarce and toxic raw materials such as lithium, cobalt and NMP. Therefore, in industrial-scale LIB manufacturing, minimizing scrap rate is crucial not only for operational efficiency but also for financial viability, product quality and environmental sustainability. During the electrode production, scrap generation may be caused by various factors such as viscosity fluctuations due to improper mixing, coating defects as a result of non-optimized coater parameters, solvent residuals after insufficient drying, or thickness deviations arising from inaccurate calendaring. Currently, digitalization of the LIB production is one of the most promising approaches to cope with these challenges. For instance, the digital twin concept creates a real-time virtual replica of the production line, enabling immediate detection of process deviations and providing manufacturers with the opportunity for instant intervention. Another example is the implementation of machine learning algorithms. In this approach, algorithms analyze the previous manufacturing data and learn the conditions that resulted with scrap formation. In this way, if non-standard process behaviors such as viscosity incompatibility, coating thickness deviations or drying temperature imbalances occur again, the production line can be monitored with real-time data flow and intervention can be made before scrap occurs. In addition, modelling techniques offer simulation of the electrode manufacturing steps through mathematical, physical or data-driven models. The application of modelling methods enables systematic evaluation of process parameters variations on product quality in a simulation environment prior to production, which contributes to a significant reduction in scrap generation. The integration of these digitalization-based methods into the equipment used in electrode production offers the advantage of minimizing the possibility of scrap production by creating a more precise and controllable process. Furthermore, through internet of things (IoT) technology, interconnected equipment can share process data in real time, enabling continuous monitoring of individual performance and parameter variations. This communication allows any deviation occurring in one piece of equipment to be instantly assessed along with its potential impact on subsequent processes. In addition to ensure high product quality and efficient use of resources, battery cell manufacturing will also benefit from predictive maintenance of the machinery, remote control with enhanced responsiveness. Knowing that data-driven decision making in battery cell production enables smarter and faster decision-making processes, seamless data flow thanks to IoT will make desired performance metrics accessible by management and engineers. As a result, chain-reaction quality issues and the risk of scrap generation can be detected during manufacturing and addressed through timely interventions. With the integration of these aforementioned decision support approaches into electrode production equipment, the potential for the establishment of fully autonomous and self-optimizing production lines is consistently increasing. Accordingly, the probability of scrap generation will be minimized through production lines where process deviations can be predicted before they occur and equipment parameters are automatically adjusted in real time. In conclusion, data-driven and human-machine collaboration-based digital factories appear to have the potential to enhance production sustainability and efficiency.

Another important point for future LIB manufacturing is flexible production lines. The applications of LIBs are rapidly expanding, creating a demand for various battery chemistries, electrode geometries, and cell types tailored to different uses. Current production lines are typically designed for a single product type and specific chemistry, lacking the flexibility to promptly and effectively meet diversity requirements. Moreover, reconfiguring these lines for different products is laborious, time-consuming, and costly. Therefore, the development and widespread adoption of flexible production lines, which are reconfigurable and adaptable, has become critical. In this context, designing electrode manufacturing equipment with a modular structure allows rapid replacement and reconfiguration of process equipment across various production scenarios. For instance, modular mixing systems used in slurry preparation can be designed as easily detachable and independently operable modules, eliminating cross-contamination risks when switching between different battery chemistries. This enables fast transitions via module swaps within the same facility for AMs like NMC, LFP, LCO, or graphite without prolonged cleaning processes or tank replacements. This approach significantly enhances production flexibility, paving the way for manufacturing lines that can quickly respond to diverse market demands. In the future, flexible production systems will pave the way for a faster product changeover between different battery types and/or formats; a high adaptability and customization without extensive CAPEX investments; cost competitive production and faster time-to-market in line with innovative ecosystem in battery manufacturing. Flexible lines have also high potential for standardized quality control by facilitating quality assurance testing protocols and resource efficiency by optimizing material use, reducing scraps – ultimately contributing to United Nations sustainability goals.

Innovative experiences gained through process-related challenges and equipment utilization issues encountered in low TRL R&D studies conducted by academia present significant opportunities for the advancement of industrial systems. First of all, academic institutions could play a role in co-development of advanced battery machinery by jointly working from the design phase until end of line tests. This will enable shorter lab-to-market and wide market acceptance for developed machinery. Since academic institutions are flexible with access to multidisciplinary expertise and tools, such collaborations will foster out-of-the-box thinking during machinery development phase. The operational know-how and practical insights obtained from academia hold substantial potential to directly contribute to the industry. These experiences can support the reduction of production error rates, improve process sustainability, and help achieve consistent product quality. Moreover, through structured academia-industry collaborations, it will be possible to cultivate a highly qualified workforce specialized in battery production equipment and proficient in the implementation of production technologies and methodologies. Such collaborations will play a key role in addressing the increasing need for skilled technical personnel in the industry. By training experts specialized in battery production equipment and processes through joint programs for students and early-career engineers, these partnerships can support talent management in battery manufacturing industry, while contributing to both production efficiency and long-term operational sustainability. Additionally, this synergy will foster the development of essential know-how and technical capacity, enabling production systems to rapidly adapt to next-generation battery chemistries and evolving process requirements. As a result, the competitiveness and resilience of the battery manufacturing industry will be significantly reinforced in the face of dynamic market demands.

In recent years, significant research efforts have focused on next-generation batteries such as Na-ion batteries (NIBs) and solid-state batteries (SSBs). In the context of both NIB and SSB electrodes, the equipment used in their fabrication is remarkably similar to that used for LIB electrodes. Therefore, developments achieved in LIB electrode production machinery make a significant contribution to NIB and SSB electrode fabrication as well. It is important to note that electrodes for SSBs can also be prepared using the conventional wet slurry mixing and coating methods, similar to electrodes for traditional LIBs. The primary distinction between SSBs and conventional LIBs lies in the state of the electrolyte, as a conventional LIBs utilize a liquid electrolyte whereas SSBs comprise a solid electrolyte. Although the equipment used in electrode manufacturing may be similar, post-fabrication optimization of the solid electrolytes in SSBs, such as enhancing ionic conductivity or improving interfacial contact, may require different equipment. In this regard, the implementation of flexible production lines would enable efficient adaptation of the same manufacturing facility to different battery technologies. Modular manufacturing machinery could be rapidly exchanged or reconfigured, allowing transitions between LIB, NIB, and SSB electrode fabrication with minimal downtime and cost. Such adaptability not only maximizes equipment utilization but also accelerates the commercialization of next generation batteries within a single production environment.

Sustainable production strategies have become another key focus in battery production. Among them, dry electrode manufacturing stands out as one of the most attractive methods for both academia and industry, primarily due to the elimination of toxic NMP solvent, a major sustainability concern in conventional processes. In this approach, the equipment requirements and operational procedures differ significantly from those used in conventional methods. For instance, in contrast to conventional wet slurry-based electrode production, a dry mixing process is required for dry electrode manufacturing. However, the more mature and widely used machines in industry (e.g., hydrodynamic shear mixers) is applicable only for the wet route, highlighting the need to develop specialized mixers that can ensure proper dispersion and homogeneity of dry electrode materials. Similarly, conventional coating equipment currently used in battery production is designed for wet slurry processes. For dry electrode production, viable alternative approaches are likewise available (discussed in detail in section 2.2.4) including techniques such as dry calendaring and electrostatic spray deposition. Despite the availability of these methods, they are not yet technologically mature for industrial-scale battery production, making them unsuitable for widespread use. Therefore, this limitation hinders the adoption of the more sustainable and environmentally friendly dry electrode manufacturing concept. Consequently, further effort and financial resources are essential to develop equipment specifically designed to enable large-scale implementation of these techniques. Furthermore, one of the main advantages of dry electrode manufacturing is the elimination of the energy-intensive drying step and the need for solvent recovery, which provides clear manufacturing and economic benefits. For existing production lines, it reduces energy consumption and operational costs, while for newly established facilities, avoiding the installation of dryers and solvent recovery systems significantly lowers initial capital expenditure. In addition, advancements in dry electrode manufacturing equipment are expected not only to enhance production efficiency and cost-effectiveness but also to contribute to lowering final product prices in the battery market and increasing accessibility for a broader consumer base. Building on these machinery-based improvements, digitalization of production lines can further

enhance the sustainability of electrode manufacturing. Real time monitoring and data-driven process optimization help reduce energy consumption, minimize material waste, and improve process consistency. Additionally, close collaboration between academia and industry is also crucial for the development of equipment required for sustainable manufacturing, as academic research provides innovative concepts and fundamental understanding, while industrial partners contribute practical knowledge and large-scale testing capabilities, ensuring that new technologies are both technically feasible and economically viable.

4. Conclusion

The LIB electrode production machinery is one of the most important parts of the LIB value chain. The diversity of electrode manufacturing equipment, their adaptability to different production approaches, and their compatibility with various electrode components play a crucial role in the fabrication of high-quality and wide-range batteries. In addition, energy consumption levels, maintenance demands, and production consistency are critical factors influencing manufacturing costs, particularly at the industrial-scale production. The proper selection and optimized use of machines in electrode manufacturing constitute a fundamental cornerstone for the production of cost-effective, high-performance, high-capacity, reliable, and efficient batteries. Therefore, in this review, we have investigated the state-of-the-art and emerging technologies used in the slurry mixing, coating, drying and calendaring steps of LIB electrode fabrication from different perspectives to provide a guide to the readers.

In the slurry mixing step, HSMs are the state-of-the-art technology adopted from laboratory-scale research to industrial level LIB production. Although BMMs, USMs and extruders have their own advantages, HSMs are widely preferred with their upsides such as less air bubble formation, high efficiency and suitability for all scales for electrode production. Furthermore, slot die coater is the most widely used machine in the coating step of industrial-scale production, while doctor blade coater is typically utilized in laboratory research. Besides, emerging dry coating techniques, such as electrostatic spray deposition and dry calendaring via rolling press, are promising technologies that are gaining increasing attention, although integration into industrial applications is still ongoing. In industrial-scale electrode manufacturing, hot air convection is the commonly utilized method in the drying step. However, due to the high energy consumption of this technique, the integration of IR dryers, as an emerging and more energy-efficient technology in terms of electrode drying, into hot air convection systems is a key focus in recent research and development efforts. However, while MW dryers are promising alternatives for the drying step, the reflection risks of MWs and high operation costs indicate that further advancements are still needed. Lastly, the roll press is the equipment used in the calendaring step and is utilized across all production scales, from laboratory to industrial levels. Despite the fact that it is the only machine used in this process, there is limited research on it, and important aspects such as its structural characteristics and operating principles in electrode fabrication remain unaddressed.

Building on the current advances and challenges in LIB manufacturing machinery, the following key areas have been identified as critical for future research and development to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and flexibility in electrode production processes:

- 1) Digital technologies such as digital twins, machine learning and modelling enable real-time monitoring of production lines. These tools help detect and correct process deviations before scrap generations. In addition, IoT implementation offers minimizing quality defects and scrap rates through equipment intercommunication.
- 2) Flexible production lines allow rapid adaptation to different battery chemistries and cell formats. Modular equipment reduces downtime and cleaning needs during product switches. This flexibility supports diverse market demands and sustainable production scalability.
- 3) Academia-industry collaboration provides valuable insights from low TRL research to improve industrial processes. It also supports training of skilled personnel specialized in battery production technologies. This partnership enhances product quality, reduces errors, and boosts long-term sustainability.
- 4) Next-generation manufacturing equipment such as ultrasonic mixers, dry coating, and laser drying promise higher efficiency and environmental benefits. Dry coating notably eliminates solvents and shortens process times. Their industrial adoption is expected to reduce costs and improve competitiveness in the battery market.

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